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USING GOOGLE SERVICES TO TEACH ENGLISH

Adilkhan E.

Master

Atyrau University

Avenue Students

Abstract

At present, new information technologies and telecommunication means have been widely used not only in scientific research and management of various social, economic and political processes, but also in the education system. The range of new forms of education using information technologies and computer networks is expanding. The rise of society to a new level, its driving force is the comprehension and application of experience and the past in the education of young people in accordance with the requirements of modern times. One of these needs is to increase cognitive activity through Internet sources. This requires a full quality of knowledge on the productive implementation of the problem and the formation of skills and abilities to use it in the practice of students. The main purpose of teaching English is the formation and development of students' communicative culture, practical training in mastering English.

Keywords: information technology, internet sources, English language, the education system.

As the political scientist T. Abduali noted: "we are very worried when the head of state raises the issue of globalization. Globalization is, simply put, the strengthening of our relations with countries that have reached a high level. One of them is language communication. To do this, it is necessary to inculcate young people to learn English, which is the language of international communication. We are acutely aware of its need over time." And Doctor of Philology, Professor, Academician of the International Academy of Pedagogical Sciences, teacher T. Tanirbergenovna continues her thought: "learning English, we do not waste time. English does not interfere with the study of the Kazakh language. We just need to understand. Because English does not compete with the state language."

Russian scientist E. M. Ryt assessed the foreign language: "the methodology of teaching a foreign language is a practical determinant of comparative linguistics." On the importance of including information technologies in the methodology of teaching a foreign language, scientist O. Tatarnikov expresses his opinion as follows: "there is evidence that a computer creates opportunities for the development of visual – imaginative thinking, motor and verbal communication skills, purposeful activity and socialization." Here, according to these scientists, you can see the importance of using information technology, the Internet when learning English and learning English. The XXI century is the era of the information society, the era of technological culture, the era of careful attitude to the outside world, human health, professional culture.

Informatization of the educational process involves improving the efficiency and quality of all levels

of the educational process, realizing the goals of developmental learning, personality-oriented learning using new information technologies.

In addition, the use of various didactic methods in information technology has its own rich history, deep content, diverse features. As you know, modernity requires the use of new technologies and active methods of spiritual, aesthetic, emotional, intellectual impact on students, the development of their personal and qualitative qualities. Because this is a guarantee of the quality of their work at school. Therefore, in the process of increasing the cognitive activity of students through Internet sources, it is necessary to introduce an increase in cognitive activity in the educational process of general educational institutions. It requires not only new information tools, but also new forms and methods of teaching, a new approach to the learning process [1].

The use of computer technologies significantly changes approaches to the development of educational material on the discipline in teaching foreign languages.

The use of Internet resources presupposes a new form of cognitive activity of students, the result of which is the formation of cognitive independence skills in students, the development of new knowledge in the field of search and orientation, replenishment and realization of knowledge independently.

The main purpose of teaching a foreign language is to develop the communicative culture of students and the skills of practical knowledge of a foreign language. The task of the teacher is to create favorable conditions for students to learn a foreign language. The Internet

resource helps to identify individual characteristics of students taking into account their skills [2].

The task of the teacher is to create appropriate conditions for practical language acquisition, to choose teaching methods that allow each student to show their activity and creativity. The task of the teacher is to increase the cognitive activity of the student in the process of learning foreign languages. Modern pedagogical technologies, such as collaborative learning, design methods, the use of new information technologies, Internet resources, help to implement a personality-oriented approach to learning, identify children's abilities, their level of learning, aptitudes, etc. individualization and differentiation of learning, taking into account the Form of working with computer training programs in foreign language lessons, include the following areas:

- learning vocabulary;
- practicing pronunciation;
- teaching dialogic and monologue speech;
- training letter;
- working out grammatical phenomena.

Opportunities and services provided by the Internet when teaching English:

- Getting information on request;
- Use of remote information sources;
- Performing tasks and exercises set by the parties of the Internet;
- Independent search by penetration into various systems;
- E-mail correspondence in the language he reads; fast delivery of information to any distance;
- Connection to the required original information [3].

Using the information resources of the global Internet, introducing them into the educational process and giving appropriate didactic explanations, it is possible to effectively solve the following ways of didactic tasks.

- Formation of materials, reading skills and abilities of varying degrees of complexity;
- Improve the skills of oral speech based on the analysis of materials obtained from the Internet;
- Improving writing skills by writing written letters, responses, preparing reports, abstracts, and other written works
- Expand cognitive knowledge, including the history and culture of the country of the language being studied, traditions and customs, features of economic development;

In English lessons, using the Internet, you can perform various didactic tasks: to form reading skills, to form writing skills, to expand the vocabulary of the student, to increase the student's interest in learning English. Students can participate in various Olympiads, competitions on the Internet. You will also have the opportunity to do interesting exercises that will go through various games with test papers. One of the achievements of mankind over the past decade is the international Internet, which has had a significant impact on the learning process. A new direction of the methodology is the use of the Internet for educational purposes. The Internet is based on the formation of the student's intercultural skills. The Internet is a multina-

tional, intercultural society of peoples, i.e. when millions of people from all over the world communicate electronically, students face real life situations. The computer does not criticize the work of students, but creates a favorable socio-psychological atmosphere, developing its own abilities and increasing their trust. Currently, the development of knowledge means the development of the level of information potential of the student [4].

When I worked at the gymnasium school No.138 in Almaty, I taught in grades 6-7. During the lesson, I myself used Google Drive and Google Presentation. It is very convenient to work on two platforms. Classes make it easier to pass. Indispensable devices for teachers. Google Services-Google Drive cloud service is very useful for teachers and students. Google Drive Cloud Service is a file storage system associated with a Google account and is accessible via the Internet. Google Drive is a file storage, processing and synchronization service. The file can be accessed via any device. Google Disk has provided secure data storage. Google Docs (Google docs) is a great opportunity to collaborate with students. You can upload and save photos, videos, documents and other important files to Google Disk. A very convenient platform for classes. We saved all the necessary documents, all the videos related to the lessons here and watched them with the students [5]. For me, it was the most necessary platform.

Google Presentation is a presentation program that is part of a free Internet-based office suite. Google is a slide editor in online presentation mode. The program offers a full set of its own convenient templates and tools of various subjects to create visually beautiful and informative slides. Diagrams, drawings, figures, beautiful designs - everything we need, we can find. A very convenient, accessible platform for explaining and discussing the lesson. I myself worked with this platform during classes. The lesson was very suitable for an explanation. I have prepared all my new classes on this platform. All presentations are also automatically saved to Google Drive [6]. The learning process through information technology will allow students to form new thinking, develop creative abilities, and provide students with a modern, innovative direction. And in English lessons, you can achieve many successes using information technology. Possession of information technologies has a positive effect on the formation of intellectual, professional, moral, spiritual, civic and other human abilities of a teacher. Promotes self-development and effective organization of the educational process. After all, a high-quality study of English is a requirement of time [7]. In conclusion: Article 8, paragraph 7 of the Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan "On Education" sets the task: "introduction of new learning technologies, informatization of education, access to international global communication networks." Consequently, the organization of the educational process at the level of the state educational standard obliges to introduce new pedagogical technologies. "In the modern world, it is very necessary to give young people a new education that meets international standards related to information technology""

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FORMATION OF INTEGRATED PERCEPTION OF THE ENVIRONMENT IN THE YOUNG SCHOOLCHILDREN IN THE LESSONS «I EXPLORE THE WORLD»

Filimonova T.

PhD in Pedagogy, Associate Professor of the Department of Primary Education of Mykolaiv V.O. Sukhomlynskiy National University, Mykolayiv, Ukraine

ФОРМУВАННЯ ЦІЛІСНОГО СПРИЙНЯТТЯ НАВКОЛИШНЬОГО СВІТУ У МОЛОДШИХ ШКОЛЯРІВ НА УРОКАХ «Я ДОСЛІДЖУЮ СВІТ»

Філімонова Т.

кандидат педагогічних наук, доцент кафедри початкової освіти Миколаївського національного університету імені В.О.Сухомлинського, Миколаїв, Україна

Abstract

The article reveals the problem of forming a holistic perception of the world around a junior student in the lessons "I explore the world". It is noted that to form in students a holistic image of the world (holistic picture of the world, worldview) is possible provided a correct understanding of its essence.

The concept of "worldview" is revealed, and it is noted that close in meaning to the concept of "worldview" are the concepts: "general scientific picture of the world", "holistic picture of the world", "worldview", "worldview" and "worldview". The difference between the concepts of "worldview" and "picture of the world" is that the worldview acts as a methodology for constructing a general scientific picture of the world.

We have determined that the process of forming a holistic picture of the world is a complex, multi-stage process. The main aspects of which can be distinguished: perception, refraction through the "I" of new knowledge and sensations; awareness of information related to mental and sensory activities; formation of one's own picture of the world in the mind of the individual. All these stages are interconnected and interdependent. There is a direct relationship between the worldview of man and knowledge. Yes, lack of knowledge makes the picture of the world of the individual incomplete. Perceptions of the world are correlated with the main components of the holistic picture of the child's world, including such concentrates as Nature, Man, Society, Culture, Science.

Thus, the formation of a holistic picture of the world is, on the one hand, the student's awareness of the many connections and dependencies between objects and phenomena of the surrounding reality, and on the other - the ability to see the world in its various aspects, from different positions: through scientific knowledge facts, image design, attitude and establishing human relationships with the outside world.

We noted that the picture of the individual's world depends on a number of objective and subjective factors. Therefore, for the younger student, an important source of spiritual life is the world of things - their essence, causation and dependence.

Анотація

У статті розкривається проблема формування цілісного сприйняття навколишнього світу у молодшого школяра на уроках «Я досліджую світ». Зазначено, що формувати в учнів цілісний образ світу (цілісну картину світу, світогляд) можливо за умови правильного розуміння його суті.

Розкрито поняття «світогляд», а також зазначено, що близькими за значенням до поняття «світогляд» є поняття: «загальна наукова картина світу», «цілісна картина світу», «світовідчуття», «світосприйняття» та «світорозуміння». Різниця між поняттями «світогляд» і «картина світу» полягає в тому, що світогляд виступає як методологія побудови загальної наукової картини світу.

Нами визначено, що процес формування цілісної картини світу – складний, багатоетапний процес. Основними аспектами якого можна виділити: сприйняття, переломлення через «я» нових знань і відчуттів; усвідомлення інформації, пов'язане з розумовою і чуттєвою діяльністю; формування власної картини світу у свідомості індивіда. Усі ці етапи взаємопов'язані та взаємозалежні. Існує пряма залежність уявлення про світ людини та знань. Так, брак знань робить картину світу особистості неповною. Уявлення про світ